

Single Port Laparoscopic Transabdominal Preperitoneal (TAPP) Repair Of Inguinal Hernias: Initial Experience And Outcome In Single Institute

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Inguinal hernia repair is the most frequently performed surgical procedure worldwide. Laparoscopic inguinal hernia repair has a number of advantages over conventional open repair. Single-incision laparoscopic surgery (SILS) was developed with the aim of reducing the invasiveness of conventional laparoscopy, and has been successfully performed by many surgeons. **Materials and Methods:** This study was conducted over a period of one year from nov 2011 to October 2012 in Department of General Surgery, Acharya sri chander college of Medical Sciences and Hospital , Sidhra, Jammu(ASCOMS). This study was conducted on 50 patients presenting to ASCOMS with uncomplicated inguinal hernia among which 25 underwent single port laparoscopic TAPP and rest 25 underwent conventional TAPP. **Observation and Results:** The mean Age, weight and height were 44.45 , 59.46 and 157.1 cm respectively which were almost same for conventional TAPP and thus no significant differences were noted. In this study 26(52%) had indirect inguinal hernia and 24(48%) had indirect inguinal hernia and the difference was statistically insignificant. Postoperative complications were significantly more in conventional TAPP. Mean hospital stay in single port TAPP was significantly lower than conventional TAPP. **Conclusion:** Thus when compared to conventional technique single port TAPP offers lesser duration of surgery and general anaesthesia, lesser postoperative complications and lesser hospital stay and early recovery.

KEYWORDS inguinal hernia , TAPP, TEP , Single port laparoscopic repair

Introduction

Inguinal hernia repair is the most frequently performed surgical procedure worldwide.[1] Laparoscopic inguinal hernia repair has several advantages over conventional open repair. Therefore, laparoscopic transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) and totally extraperitoneal (TEP) techniques are frequently preferred.[2-4]

When comparing the two techniques, TAPP is easier to learn and may be associated with a shorter learning curve.[5] Recent studies have been focused on minimising further the invasiveness of laparoscopy by reducing the number of incisions and the port size. In this way, pain and complications associated with incisions were decreased. Single-incision laparoscopic surgery (SILS) was developed to reduce the invasiveness of conventional laparoscopy and has been successfully performed by many surgeons.[6-8]

Material and Methods

This study was conducted over one year from Nov 2011 to October 2012 in the Department of General Surgery, Acharya Sri Chander College of Medical Sciences and Hospital, Sidhra, Jammu (ASCOMS).

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Table 1 Demography.

DEMOGRAPHY	CONVENTIONAL TAPP	SINGLE PORT TAPP	p-value
Mean Age	44.06	44.46	0.27
Mean wt(kg)	60.56	59.46	0.32
Mean Ht(cm)	159.46	157.23	0.12

Table 2 Mean operative time of single port TAPP was significantly less than conventional TAPP (P<.01).

GROUP	NO OF PATIENTS	TIME(mins)
CONVENTIONAL	25	95.5
SINGLE PORT TAPP	25	81.5

This study was conducted on 50 patients presenting to AS-COMS with uncomplicated inguinal hernia, among which 25 underwent single port laparoscopic TAPP and rest 25 underwent conventional TAPP.

Inclusion criteria

1. Patients with uncomplicated symptomatic inguinal hernia.
2. Unilateral inguinal hernias.
3. Primary hernia or first recurrences.

Exclusion criteria

Patients bedridden with cancer were excluded from the study. Subjects with resolved case of prostate and other forms of cancer were also excluded from the study.

1. Comorbid conditions making patient unfit for GA.
2. Complicated hernias.
3. Intrabdominal or pelvic malignancy.
4. Advanced pregnancy.
5. Morbid obesity or ascites.

Patients were assessed for:

- Demography.
- Operative time.
- Need to convert to either conventional TAPP or open surgery.
- Postoperative complications.
- Postoperative hospital stay.

Equipment

- Telescope 30 degrees.
- Co2 insufflator.
- Endoscopic video CCD chip camera
- High-resolution colour monitor
- Halogen xenon light source
- Universal light guide cable
- Videocassette recorder
- Co2 cylinder and connecting pipe to insufflators
- Electric cautery
- Suction apparatus

Basic surgical instruments

- Verres needle
- Reduction tube
- Grasping forceps
- Dissecting forceps
- Scissors
- Laparoscopic Babcock forceps
- Spatula dissector
- Single port with trochars 10mm and 5mm.

Single Port Repair (SPL)

Specialised equipment for SPL falls under two categories that is access port and hand instruments. There are several different access ports:

1. GelPOINT from applied medical.
2. SILS from Covidien (used in this study).

Hand-held instruments come in two configurations standard or articulating. Laparoscopic SPA was done through one trochar with one instrument that has an optical lens and channel for grasper. After inserting trochar at umbilicus using semi-open technique, intraperitoneal anatomical landmarks of inguinal hernia were identified.

Operative steps

1. Incising the peritoneum.
2. Raising the peritoneal flap.
3. Dissection of medial peritoneum and Direct sac.
4. Lateral dissection.
5. Dissection of indirect inguinal hernia sac and peritoneum within the cord.
6. Preparation and site from the mesh.
7. Retroperitonealisation.

Table 3 Postoperative complications.

GROUP	NO OF PATIENTS	Complications	Reoccurrence
CONVENTIONAL	25	6 (24%)	0
SINGLE PORT TAPP	25	1(%%)	0

Table 4 Mean operative time of single port TAPP was significantly less than conventional TAPP ($p < .01$).

GROUP	NO OF PATIENTS	Hospital Stay(days)
CONVENTIONAL	25	3.5
SINGLE PORT TAPP	25	1.75

Observation and Results

The mean age, weight and height were 44.45, 59.46 and 157.1 cm respectively, which were almost same for conventional TAPP and thus no significant differences were noted.

In this study, 26(52%) had an indirect inguinal hernia, and 24(48%) had an indirect inguinal hernia, and the difference was statistically insignificant. All the patients (100%) had a unilateral inguinal hernia.

Postoperative complications were significantly more in conventional TAPP ($p < 0.01$) with none converted to conventional TAPP or open surgery.

Discussion

Fifty patients who presented with chief complaints of groin swelling of one or more months were included in our study excluding the pediatric patients. In our study of 25 patients, each who underwent single-port TAPP and conventional TAPP the mean age were 44.86 and 44.06 respectively which were similar to study done by Tai HC et al 9 (46.5years), Ertem M et al 10 (53 years).

In our study, the meantime for single port TAPP was 81.5 min which was significantly lesser to conventional TAPP as in the study by Tai HC et al. who successfully operated on 24 patients with a mean operative time of 83.5 mins and none was converted to conventional TAPP. Similarly, in a study by Sato et al [11], who successfully treated 35 patients with a mean operative time of 91.2 mins. In a study of 47 patients by Etem M et al., mean operative time was 96.48 mins. The mean operative time in our study of 25 patients for conventional TAPP was 95.5 mins while in study done by Sato H et al. was 86.1 mins.

In our study of 25 patients with single port TAPP, postoperative complications were reported in 1 (4%) patient who developed seroma, which was treated with repeated aspiration. Similarly, Tai H et al. in his study found 2 patients (12.5%) suffering from postoperative complications. Similarly, for conventional TAPP in our study of 25 patients, 6(24%) had postoperative complications, 5(20%) developed urinary retention and 1 (4%) developed postoperative umbilical hernia from the umbilical port which was operated after six months. Hawasli A et al[12], performed conventional TAPP for recurrent inguinal hernia developed postoperative complications in 18 patients (13%) which include 15 hematomas, two seromas and one urinary retention. Reoccurrence occurred in one patient (0.7%) in whom staples were not used.

In our study of 25 patients with single port TAPP, the mean

postoperative hospital stay was 1.75 days which was significantly lesser than conventional TAPP (3.5 days), which was in accordance to study done by JiHoon Kim et al[13] and Lee YS et al[14] with a mean hospital stay of 2.15 days and 2 days respectively. Thus when compared to conventional technique single port TAPP offers:

1. Lesser duration of surgery and general anaesthesia
2. Lesser postoperative complications
3. Lesser hospital stay and early recovery
4. Almost no reoccurrence.

The main disadvantage of single port TAPP includes a limited range of movement due to the proximity of working ports, limited triangulation.

Conclusion

Single port TAPP using same method and instrument as in conventional TAPP offers to be safe and efficient with minimum reoccurrences and shorter hospital stay.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in this study.

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Ethics Committee

None.

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